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The Transformation of Workers from Unstable to Stable in the Italian Regions

It grew on average by 33.52% between 2014 and 2020

Istat calculates the transformation from unstable jobs to stable workers. The indicator is calculated as the percentage of those employed in unstable jobs at time t0 (temporary employees + collaborators) who one year later have a stable job (permanent employees) out of the total number of people employed in unstable jobs at time t0. Source: Istat, Labor Force Survey.

Ranking of the Italian regions for the value of the transformation of unstable workers into stable ones in 2020. Veneto is in first place for the value of the transformation of workers from unstable to stable with a value equal to 31.10 units, followed by Lombardy with an amount of 28.60 units, and from Molise with a value of 27.00. In the middle of the table are Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 23.70, followed by Marche and Lazio with a value of 21.10 units. Campania closes the ranking with a value of 15.20 units, Puglia with an amount of 12.80 units and Calabria with a value of 9.20 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in the transformation of unstable workers into stable ones between 2014 and 2020. Sicily is in first place in terms of value of the transformation of unstable workers into stable ones between 2014 and 2020 with a value of 92.55% or equal to an amount of 8.7 units going from 9.4 units up to a value of 18.1 units. Basilicata follows with a variation from an amount of 8.9 units up to 16.8 units or a variation of 7.9 units equal to 88.76%. Abruzzo follows with a variation from an amount of 14.1 units up to 25.2 units or equal to a variation of 11.1 units equal to 78.72%. In the middle of the table is Umbria with a variation from 16.8 units in 2014 up to 24 in 2020 or a variation of 7.2 units equal to 42.86%. Molise follows with a variation from an amount of 18.9 units in 2014 up to a value of 27 units in 2020 or equal to a variation of 8.1 units equivalent to a value of 42.86%. Sardinia follows with a variation from an amount of 12.3 units in 2014 up to 17.1 units in 2020 or equal to a variation of 4.8 units equal to 39.02%. Liguria closes the ranking with a variation from 19.00 units in 2014 to 19.2 in 2020, i.e. a variation of 0.2 units equal to 1.05%. Friuli Venezia Giulia follows with a variation from an amount of 20.8 units in 2014 up to 19.7 units in 2020 or equal to a variation of -1.1 units equal to -5.29%. Calabria closes the ranking with a variation from an amount of 10.2 units in 2014 up to a value of 9.2 units in 2020 or equal to a variation of -1.00 units equal to -9.8%. On average, the value of the transformation of workers from unstable to stable grew from an amount of 16.01 units in 2014 up to 21.37 units in 2020 corresponding to an amount of 5.37 units or equal to an amount of 33.52 %.

The transformation of workers from unstable to stable in the Italian macro-regions between 2014 and 2020. The transformation of workers from unstable to stable in the Islands grew from 10.1 units up to 17.8 units or equal to a variation of 7.7 units equal to 76.24%. The transformation of workers from unstable to stable in the North-East grew by 45.65% between 2014 and 2020, going from an amount of 18.4 units up to a value of 26.8 units or equal to an amount of 8.4 units. The transformation of workers from unstable to stable in the Italian macro-regions between 2014 and 2020 in the North

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grew from an amount of 19.5 units up to a value of 26.9 units or equal to an amount of 7.4 units equal to an amount of 37.95%. The transformation of workers from unstable to stable in the Center grew from an amount of 17.6 units up to 23 units or equal to an amount of 5.4 units equal to 30.68%. The transformation of workers from unstable to stable in the North-West grew from an amount of 20.6 units up to 26.9 units equal to an amount of 6.3 units equal to an amount of 30.58%. In Southern Italy, the transformation of workers from unstable to stable between 2014 and 2020 grew from an amount of 12.8 units in 2014 to 14.8 in 2020 or equal to a variation of 2 units equal to 15.63 %.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The data shows the presence of two clusters:

- *Cluster 1:* Puglia, Sicily, Calabria, Campania, Basilicata, Valle d'Aosta, Sardinia;
- *Cluster 2:* Piedmont, Tuscany, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Umbria, Lombardy, Emilia Romagna, Lazio, Veneto, Trentino Alto Adige, Marche, Liguria, Molise, Abruzzo.

From the point of view of the average value, it appears that Cluster 2 is higher than Cluster 1. A contrast therefore arises between the regions of the Centre-North, which have high values of the variable analysed, and the regions of Southern Italy which have reduced. There are, however, exceptions. Valle d'Aosta, despite being a northern region, is included in Cluster 1 and on the contrary Molise and Abruzzo, despite being regions of Southern Italy, are part of Cluster 2.

Conclusions. The transformation of workers from unstable to stable increased in almost all regions between 2014 and 2020 by an average amount of 33.52%. However, there are Italian regions in which between 2014 and 2020 the value of the variable analysed decreased, namely: Friuli Venezia Giulia with -5.29% and Calabria with a value of -9.8%. There is a significant contrast between Central-Northern Italy and Southern Italy in terms of the transformation of workers from unstable to stable with a dominance of the northern regions compared to the southern regions. There is therefore a significant improvement in the Italian regions in terms of growth of stable workers even if the stabilization of the working position does not save the worker from poverty due to low incomes and the presence of the "working poor".

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

2014 2015 2016 2017 2018 2019 2020

